

A Review on Impact of Global Climate Change on Microorganisms

Arghya Chakravorty¹, Moharana Choudhury², Joystu Dutta³, Rinku Devi⁴, Kumar Deepak⁵, Rehab A. Rayan⁶

1. School of Bio Sciences & Technology, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore - 632014 India
2. Voice of Environment, Guwahati, Assam, India
3. Department of Environmental Science, University Teaching Department, Sant Gahira Guru University, Ambikapur (CG.)-497001 India
4. Indian Institute Of Forest Management, Bhopal 462003, India
5. United Nation Development Program, India
6. Department of Epidemiology, High Institute of Public Health, Alexandria University, Alexandria – 21526, Egypt

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Climate Change affects almost all life forms on earth during the evolutionary age of Anthropocene, the current age in which we live. Microorganisms form the basis of ancestral life forms and are crucial in our studies related to the cause and impacts of climate change on a global scale. 'Microorganisms' are ascribed as any microscopic organism or virus not visible to the naked eye (smaller than 50 μm) that can exist in a unicellular, multicellular (for example, differentiating species), aggregate (for example, biofilm) or viral form. In addition to microscopic bacteria, archaea, eukaryotes and viruses, we discuss certain macroscopic unicellular eukaryotes (for example, larger marine phytoplankton) and wood-decomposing fungi.

It is not only important to study how micro-organisms impact global climate change (including production and consumption of greenhouse gases) but also how they will be affected by climate change and other associated anthropogenic activities. The impacts of climate change on larger plants and animals are well documented in scientific literature. Microbes, in contrast do not find equal attention in global climate change studies. Invisible to the naked eye and intangible, the abundance (~10³⁰ total bacteria and archaea) and diversity of microorganisms form the foundations of a healthy global ecosystem; i.e., Total abundance of bacteria and archaea on earth's surface is estimated to about 1.2×10³⁰ cells which are spread across the five big habitats; deep oceanic subsurface, upper oceanic sediments, deep continental subsurface, soil and oceans as per studies forwarded by (Flemming and Wuertz, 2019). The human effects on microorganisms are less obvious and certainly less characterized,

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a major concern is that changes in microbial biodiversity and activities will affect the resilience of all other organisms and hence their ability to respond to climate change. Microorganisms play a key role in carbon and nutrient cycling, animal (including human) and plant health, agriculture and the global food web. They live in extreme situations viz., extremophiles including thermophiles (high temperature zones), acidophiles (highly acidic regions), alkalophiles (highly alkaline areas), halophiles (living in high salt concentrations), xerophiles (living in low water availability) as well as radioresistant microbes. Hence, they are ideal candidates for climate change researches across the globe. Microorganisms date back to the origin of life on Earth at least 3.8 billion years ago, and they will likely exist well beyond any future extinction events. The immense microbial diversity and their varied responses to environmental changes make it challenging to determine their role in ecosystem. In this research paper, we attempt to establish correlation between microorganisms, macroscopic organisms and climate change, and put scientific community on notice that the microscopic majority can no longer be the unseen elephant in the room. Our approach in the road towards sustainable development would be limited unless we appreciate the microbial existence and the multifaceted applications of microbial communities in our daily life which is very broad ranging (from beneficial to harmful as well as inert). The recent incidents of bird flu incidents in India to Corona virus outbreak in Asia are a testimony to the fact that microbial existence can lead to extreme pathogenicity paralyzing the entire socio-economic system. Similarly, beneficial roles of microbes cannot be undermined as stated earlier. This paper focusses on the influences of climate change on microbial community composition and function, physiological responses and evolutionary adaptation. The microorganism–climate connections and impacts of anthropogenic stress factors such as types of pollution (local, regional and global) as well as eutrophication are also addressed. The bioaccumulation of xenobiotic and the role of microbial fauna in remediation are also noted. The role of microbes is extremely crucial in different biomes across almost all ecosystems (from terrestrial to marine) and biomes (from tundra to tropical) and biogeographic zones (from mountains to deserts to islands). The roles are varied, dynamic and pivotal for sustenance of other life forms on earth. For example, by fixing carbon and nitrogen, and remineralizing organic matter, marine microorganisms form the basis of ocean food webs and thus global carbon and nutrient cycles or the role in litter decomposition and organic matter release in the soils of a tropical rain forest ensure the proper cycling of nutrients and minerals across the trophic levels thus increasing the Net Primary Productivity. The impact of elevated greenhouse gas concentrations on ocean temperature, acidification, stratification, mixing, thermohaline circulation, nutrient supply, irradiation and extreme weather events affects the marine microbiota in ways that have substantial environmental consequences, including major shifts in productivity, marine food webs, carbon export

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and burial in the seabed as studied by various scientists (Hurd, 2018; Gao, 2012; Boyd, 2013; Pörtner, 2014; Brennan and Collins, 2015; Hutchins, et al., 2016; Hutchins, et al., 2017; Rintoul, et al., 2018).

Climate change perturbs interactions between species and forces species to adapt, migrate and be replaced by others or go extinct (Hutchins, 2017; Hoffman, 2011). Ocean warming, acidification, eutrophication and overuse (for example, fishing, tourism) together cause the decline of coral reefs and may cause ecosystems shifts towards macroalgae (Hughes, 1994; Bellwood, 2006; Hoegh-Goldberg, 2007; Mumby, 2007; Enochs, 2007) and benthic cyanobacterial mats (De Bakker, 2017; Ford, 2018). The capacity for corals to adapt to climate change is strongly influenced by the responses of their associated microorganisms, including microalgal symbionts and bacteria (Ziegler, et al., 2017; Torda, 2017; Quigley, et al., 2018). Corals are a refuge to innumerable number of living communities which are crucial for host health, for example by recycling the waste products, by provisioning essential nutrients and vitamins and by assisting the immune system to fight pathogens (Bourne, et al., 2016). Natural as well as anthropogenic infringements on marine environment lead to coral bleaching causing rapid and permanent changes in the coral micro biome. Such shifts undoubtedly influence the ecological functions and stability of the coral–microorganism system, potentially affecting the capacity and pace at which corals adapt to climate change, and the relationships between corals and other components of the reef ecosystem (Bourne, et al., 2016; Webster, 2017). Very few studies have focused on evolutionary potential of micro-organisms and their adaptive capacities to changing climate scenarios on a spatio-temporal scale. From ocean acidifications, to sea-level rise, from temperature fluctuations to species loss, from anthropogenic pollution to erratic ocean current patterns, from increased frequency of natural disasters to radioactive fallout; the global climate variability has registered unpredictable consequences. Thus, the study of microbes finds relevance here. They are the ideal candidates to understand the effects of global climate change as well as ways to mitigate and adapt to such changes in a sustainable manner.

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